

Spatial Relationship Criterion #3: Polygons Intersect Polygons

The "Polygons Intersect Polygons" spatial relationship criterion is a powerful tool for analyzing how different polygon features overlap within a specific area. For example, it can help identify where zoning areas (such as residential, commercial, or industrial zones) intersect with specific land use designations.

Similarly, it can show where protected areas, overlap with land designated for other uses, such as agriculture or development.

In cadastral mapping, this criterion allows users to see where property boundaries might intersect with municipal or administrative boundaries.

In our practical case, when planning large infrastructure projects like utility networks, this tool helps visualize how planned routes intersect with existing property boundaries, aiding in optimization and minimizing disruption.

Now, let's dive into how this is done;

Fig. 1 A cadastral basemap with a heating network pipeline dataset displayed in SGIS Desktop.

Since we already have our dataset loaded from the previous example, in this case, we need to create a buffer around the heating network pipeline to identify which land parcels fall within the designated project area. We'll set the buffer to 10 meters on both sides of the pipeline and check which land parcels are impacted by the project.

To begin, we'll open the 'Buffer' function.

This function is easily accessible in the main toolbar at the top of SGIS Desktop's user interface.

Fig. 2 The 'Buffer' function, located in the main toolbar at the top of SGIS Desktop's user interface, is selected to begin the process of creating a buffer around the pipeline.

Fig. 3 The 'Create Buffer' function is activated, and a new buffer layer is added to the Layers List, showing the 10-meter buffer zone around the pipeline.

After configuring the settings, we click 'Create Buffer'.

A new layer with the buffer polygon immediately appears in the Layers List. Now that the buffer is created, we can use the 'Select by Layer' function to identify where the two polygon layers overlap and intersect.

Fig. 4 The newly created buffer polygon layer is visible in the Layers List, representing the 10-meter buffer around the pipeline.

Fig. 5 The 'Select by Layer' dialog window is open, with the 'Polygons Intersect Polygons' mode selected from the 'Selection Mode' dropdown menu.

When the 'Select by Layer' dialog window opens, we start by choosing our mode from the 'Selection Mode' dropdown menu, selecting 'Polygons Intersect Polygons'.

Next, under the 'Layer to be selected' dropdown, we choose 'Level 11 – Land Parcels'.

For the third dropdown, we select the 'Buffer 10m' layer.

Fig. 6 The 'Layer to be selected' dropdown is set to 'Level 11 – Land Parcels', indicating the layer of land parcels for selection.

Fig. 7 The third dropdown menu shows the 'Buffer 10m' layer selected, which will be used to identify intersections with the land parcels.

Finally, we click 'Select' to finish the process.

All polygon features that meet the criteria will instantly be selected and highlighted in the Graphics panel.

In this example, the highlighted polygons appear in red, though this is fully customizable and can be adjusted based on user preferences.

Fig. 8 The 'Select' button is clicked, finalizing the process and highlighting the selected polygons in the Graphics panel.

Fig. 9 The Graphics panel displays the selected polygons, highlighted in red to show where they meet the criteria. The highlight color can be customized according to user preferences.

One great feature of SGIS is the 'Pan to Element' function found in the Selected Elements panel. After making a selection, the highlighted elements will not only be visible on the graphics panel, but they will also be listed in the Selected Elements panel. Users can click on each element individually, and its attributes will be displayed in a convenient tree-like format.

This is particularly useful when you want to quickly check the attribute values of a selected element without having to open the entire attributes table.

If you right-click on any item in the list, a menu will pop up, and the first option will be 'Pan to Element.' This feature makes it easy to zoom in on the selected element in the graphics panel, eliminating the need for a manual search.

Fig.10 A context menu appearing after right-clicking on a selected element in the list, featuring the 'Pan to Element' option for easy navigation to the highlighted feature in the graphics panel.

Fig.11 Clicking the 'Pan to Element' function navigates you to the selected feature on the graphics panel, providing greater visual clarity.

We can easily separate all the polygons into a new layer using the one-click function 'Selected Elements in New Layer' for further processing and analysis of their geometry and attributes. After naming the new layer, it will be created instantly, and with that, we'll wrap up this procedure.

Fig.12 The process of separating all selected polygons into a new layer using the ‘Selected Elements in New Layer’ function for further analysis of their geometry and attributes. After naming the layer, it is created instantly, completing the procedure.